

The European Satellite Centre: Geospatial Intelligence at the Services of the EU and its Member States

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Abstract

In view of an increasingly tense geopolitical landscape, caused by conflicts such as Russia's aggression in Ukraine and crises in the Middle East and Africa, the EU's need for an autonomous and responsive decision-making capacity in security and defence has drastically increased. The European Union Satellite Centre (SatCen) in Torrejón / Madrid is the EU's central provider of imagery and geospatial analysis services for CFSP/CSDP. Working under the political guidance of its Member States, the Centre plays a crucial role in enhancing the EU's situational awareness at the nexus of external and internal security. It has become an essential capacity for swift and decisive action, in direct support to key intelligence and security actors in Europe. The article traces SatCen's evolution from its establishment in 1992 as a strategic Western European Union initiative to its current function as the EU's agency at the crossroads of space, defense and security. Beyond strategic situational awareness, the Centre supports EU military operations and civilian missions, disaster relief operations, and collaborates with European agencies like FRONTEX and strategic partners such as the UN. It also acts as the entrusted entity for the Copernicus Support for External and Security Action (SESA) service. To stay ahead of the rapid evolution in data management and secure processing, SatCen invests heavily into advanced technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI). Through its timely and accurate geospatial intelligence services, the Centre functions as Europe's "eyes from the sky", supporting EU decision-making by exploiting data coming from space assets.

Keywords

Geospatial Intelligence (GEOINT); European Union Satellite Centre (SatCen); Situational Awareness; EU Strategic Compass; Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP); Space-based Intelligence

1. Introduction

The geopolitical landscape is becoming increasingly tense, as demonstrated by Russia's war of aggression in Ukraine as well as rapidly evolving crises and wars in the Middle East and Africa. In this context, European *strategic autonomy* has become more vital than ever¹. This applies especially to the domain of security, defence and space aligned with the Strategic Compass objective to enhance the EU's capacity to act swiftly and decisively in response to emerging threats.

In this context, situational awareness is an essential capability on which effective decision-making is based, across the full spectrum from operational to the top political level. As Europe's "eyes from the sky", the European Union Satellite Centre (SatCen) in Torrejón (Madrid) is the EU's geospatial intelligence agency, providing analysis services to the EU member states, its institutions and international partners.

2. SatCen's path

In 2022, SatCen celebrated its 30th anniversary, marking three decades of dedicated service in geospatial intelligence. The origins of the Centre date back to 1991, when the Western European Union (WEU) Ministerial Council, composed of Foreign and Defence Ministers, convened on 27 June in Vianden, Luxembourg, and made the strategic decision to establish a satellite data interpretation centre. Later that year, on 19 November, the WEU Council of Ministers met in Bonn and chose Torrejón Airbase, near Madrid in Spain, as the Centre's location. Formally created as a body of the WEU, its mission was to provide actionable geospatial intelligence analysis services, based on satellite imagery and other relevant data, to support the European security and defence efforts.

The creation of this Centre in the early 1990s was a visionary initiative, shaped by the strategic minds surrounding WEU Deputy Secretary, Mr. Horst Holthoff. He pushed for an independent WEU military capability to exploit satellite imagery for defence purposes². In recognition of his strategic foresight, his name was given to the Centre's main meeting room³.

One of the Centre's earliest support missions in 1996 was assisting on-site inspectors in Kosovo in verifying the dismantling of armaments and equipment, a milestone in operational support. The WEU's experimental capability for situational awareness during crisis events proved so successful that it was transferred to the EU in 2002, then re-named the European Union Satellite Centre (SatCen), by decision of the Council of the European Union. And until today, it has remained a unique operational geospatial analysis agency in the EU's security and defence toolbox⁴.

A year later, in 2003, the European Security Strategy was introduced, marking a pivotal moment as the EU began launching military operations and civilian missions. SatCen, in coherence with the European Security Strategy, was mandated to enhance the decision-making of the European Union in the field of Common Foreign and Security Policy (CFSP), in particular the European Security and Defence Policy (ESDP), renamed the Common Security

and Defence Policy (CSDP) in 2009. The first EU operation supported by SatCen was EUFOR Althea in Bosnia and Herzegovina⁵.

The Council Decision "European Space Policy: ESDP and Space" of 2004 emphasised the critical role of the SatCen in bolstering the European Security and Defence Policy through satellite imagery analysis for intelligence, early warning, and crisis management operations.⁶ It highlighted SatCen's cooperation with EU entities, such as the Joint Research Centre and other key actors, to improve decision-making and effectively tackle capability gaps, thereby strengthening the EU's capacity to address security threats.

The European External Action Service (EEAS) was created in 2011 and over time it became one of SatCen's main users¹. Following this, in 2016, the *Global Strategy for the EU's Foreign and Security Policy* was published, reinforcing the EU's commitment to a stronger and more autonomous security and defence framework. In 2022, the EU Strategic Compass identified space as a critical strategic domain, paving the way for the first Council Conclusions on the *EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence* in November 2023, to address relevant CSDP challenges including protecting space assets and deterring threats.

SatCen is now a pillar of the EU's strategic autonomy. By providing fast, reliable and accurate geospatial intelligence services, the Centre strengthens the EU's ability to take autonomous decisions in security and defence, crisis management and foreign policy. It is SatCen's mission to enhance operational effectiveness by providing support for both civilian missions — such as humanitarian aid, disaster relief, and emergency management — and military operations. Currently the EU is engaged in 21 civilian and military missions, including military and naval operations⁷. European engagement worldwide centres on peacekeeping efforts, conflict prevention, international security, upholding the rule of law, combating piracy, enhancing maritime security, and supplying military equipment and support to EU partners. SatCen thus supports national as much as EU leaders, providing situational awareness to support their strategic priorities on both national and collective security challenges.

3. Operations

The Geospatial Intelligence (GEOINT) discipline integrates multiple elements, including mapping, cartography, imagery analysis, and imagery intelligence. Its core principle is to consolidate all available data related to a specific geographic location and analyse it to produce actionable information. These insights are then transformed into user-friendly products designed to support decision-makers at political and operational levels.

¹ In 2014 the COUNCIL DECISION 2014/401/CFSP of 26 June 2014 revised the Centre's mission and activities. Article 2 states that: "SATCEN shall support the decision making and actions of the Union in the field of the CFSP and in particular the CSDP, including European Union crisis management missions and operations, by providing, at the request of the Council or the HR, products and services resulting from the exploitation of relevant space assets and collateral data, including satellite and aerial imagery, and related services."

SatCen is a task-based agency, which means “everything starts with a question, or more precisely with many questions”⁸. The request which could e.g. originate from a Member State or from within the European External Action Service (EEAS) are then prioritised by the EU High Representative, according to political guidance given by the Council.

SatCen’s analysis room serves as the core of the Centre, where highly skilled analysts — drawn from both military and civilian backgrounds — work on large screens displaying satellite imagery and other suitable data sources. Organised into several specialised teams, this structure is optimised for high performance in a fast-paced operational environment, reaching an output of approximately 6,000 products annually⁹.

4. Engagement

Which specific activities does SatCen support? The counter-piracy naval operation EUNAVFOR ATALANTA off the Horn of Africa, EUNAVFOR MED IRINI, a naval operation aiming at enforcing the arms embargo in Libya, as well as EUNAVFOR ASPIDES in the Red Sea are just a few examples. The Centre also contributes to civilian missions for border monitoring or the assessment of military activities, like EUMM Georgia or the EU Mission in Armenia¹⁰.

Another essential and time-critical aspect of SatCen’s mission is its support for disaster relief and rescue operations: in October 2024, torrential rains devastated Valencia in Spain, resulting in over 200 fatalities, submerging streets and homes, and displacing hundreds of residents. In response, Spanish authorities launched an emergency operation to coordinate relief efforts. As the full scale of the disaster became clear, the responsible units of the Spanish Ministry of Defence activated SatCen to support its emergency operations.

In response to this urgent request, the Centre established an ad-hoc operations team, working around the clock to provide critical geospatial intelligence. Within six hours, the team delivered its first mapping product, followed by a series of additional outputs. The intelligence products enabled the Spanish authorities to assess accessible and restricted (“no-go”) areas within the affected region. This information proved instrumental in allowing emergency rescue teams to take informed decisions for optimising search and rescue operations.

Evacuation Route Analysis (Product Example)

Maputo, MOZAMBIQUE

SatCen also closely collaborates with other EU agencies and international partners focusing on common security challenges. Most notably, the Centre is supporting the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (FRONTEX) on migration issues. In 2025, this collaboration

will mark 10 years, representing a significant milestone in EU institutional interoperability. Joint efforts are focused on combating irregular immigration and cross-border crime. For the last decade, SatCen has provided more than 6000 geospatial products and services to Frontex¹¹. This effective collaboration is taking place as part of the Border Security service of Copernicus, the EU’s flagship space programme.

International users of SatCen’s services include the Organisation for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE) and the Organisation for the Prohibition of Chemical Weapons (OPCW). The requests typically involve facility assessments, analysis of surrounding areas, and road network evaluations.

Mauritania - Possible departure point for illegal migration

www.satcen.europa.eu

5. Capabilities Development and Training

SatCen continuously invests into expanding and further developing its capabilities, and in this effort collaborates closely with relevant national and EU entities like the European Commission and European Defence Agency (EDA), and international partners as European Space Agency (ESA)¹². In line with its mandate, the Centre focuses on service evolution, synergy and complementarity, continuous improvement, innovation, and knowledge transfer.

As a special focus complementing its mission, SatCen has established strategic cooperation across various components of the EU Space Programme. Also, within the framework of EU research and innovation initiatives, such as Horizon Europe, SatCen has successfully implemented projects aligned with and supporting its core mission.

The evolving global security environment has highlighted the necessity for European strategic autonomy, driving key EU security initiatives. As an operational geospatial analysis

entity, SatCen plays a pivotal role in their implementation, strengthening the EU’s capacity to respond effectively to emerging crises. The Centre’s collaboration across the EU in space, defense and security enables the deployment of cutting-edge technologies for its operational use as well as the collective benefit of the EU and its Member States.

In a key operational function, SatCen serves as the entrusted entity for Copernicus Support for External and Security Action (SESA). The Centre’s engagement in maritime security and border surveillance in cooperation with Frontex, which is a clear demonstration of interoperability, complementarity and synergies, in line with the Centre’s mandate.

In addition to its research and innovation activities, SatCen provides specialised training courses to further develop geospatial capabilities for its staff as well as across Member States and users. These trainings cover essential topics like data processing and imagery analysis, as well as advanced training in Synthetic Aperture Radar imagery, industrial site interpretation, and nuclear facility analysis: in 2024 alone, the Centre recorded almost 3.000 attendees per day at SatCen courses.

6. High-Tech

Processing large amounts of data from a wide range of satellites would be impossible without the extensive computing capacities available today. The Centre maintains extensive on-site data storage and processing capacities, but - more importantly - it hosts the first ever “EU SECRET” cloud service. This important innovation is available since 2021, providing its users with real-time access to secure operational services and processes including an innovative and operational AI factory¹³.

Further, the development and integration of Artificial Intelligence tools into the operational process has significantly enhanced efficiency in satellite image analysis. For instance, when examining maritime imagery, traditional methods require analysts to manually inspect each section for relevant details. AI, however, can automatically identify small vessels, such as migrant boats, within vast oceanic areas. To ensure the required level of accuracy and reliability, and while the AI tool is providing effective semi-automatic support, the final output is still produced under the control and supervision of the essential expertise of highly trained, experienced analysts¹⁴.

7. Challenges

In line with the continuously growing level of EU ambition in security and defence, as well as responding to the drastic changes in the European security landscape, SatCen has increased its output about tenfold in the past decade. This trend is multiplied by increasing demands on product complexity, speed of delivery, and quality expectations¹⁵.

To stay ahead of the quickly evolving geopolitical context, as much as preparing for the requirements expressed in the EU Strategic Compass and the EU Space Strategy for Security and Defence, the Member States have mandated the Centre to implement an ambitious development plan, further increasing the Centre's operational capacity over the next years. SatCen will thus continue its investment in IT, data and expert staff, to meet the challenges ahead and to satisfy the demands posed by the EU and its Member States for state-of-the-art geospatial intelligence services in the 21st century.

8. The way forward

In the current geopolitical context of evolving threats to European security and stability, SatCen as the geospatial intelligence agency remains a key asset for the EU and its Member States, with the mission to support situational awareness and thus strengthen the EU's strategic autonomy, particularly for the CSDP. The Centre will continue to operate within the guidelines provided by – inter alia - the Strategic Compass and the EU Space Strategy for Security and Defense, while also responding to further challenges in non-proliferation and space, the maritime domain, the climate and environmental crisis and hybrid warfare.

To meet these evolving requirements, SatCen is establishing a dedicated maritime analysis team, while also expanding capabilities in AI and cybersecurity to counter emerging threats. Continued investments in automation and machine learning will improve scalability and efficiency, ensuring timely and reliable analysis processes. Additionally, reinforcing the training unit will allow SatCen to better support Member States and key institutional partners in decision-making for security, crisis management, and defence operations.

Further projects of high priority are the Centre's potential role in the future Earth Observation Governmental Service (EOGS) and the envisioned Climate and Environment Security Data and Analysis Hub (CESDA). These initiatives aim to enhance Europe's climate situational awareness and security foresight.

SatCen will thus continue to serve as Europe's "eyes from the sky", delivering tailor-made, user-driven geospatial intelligence services to support the EU's decision-making in security and defence. Through its advanced analysis capabilities, the Centre plays a pivotal role in

supporting European security and defence, equipping decision-makers with the intelligence necessary to respond effectively to crises, threats, and strategic challenges.

9. References

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Short Biography:

Rear Admiral Louis Tillier became Director of the EU Satellite Centre (SatCen) on 1 June 2024, following his appointment by the SatCen Board and confirmation by Josep Borrell, having served as Deputy Director since September 2021. His naval career, commencing in 1995, included service on various vessels and significant responsibilities, alongside advanced engineering training in telecommunications, culminating in his role as Joint Staff Program Officer for Defence Satellite Communications, contributing to EDA and NATO SatCom groups. He commanded the French Ship Dupuy de Lôme and the Maritime Intelligence Centre, before transitioning to the French Space Command, where he oversaw European and international space cooperation, leading efforts on European space security and defence, collaborating extensively with EU stakeholders and allies, prior to his SatCen appointment.